

**ELECTRONIC COMMERCE AND ITS DEVELOPMENT STAGES IN
PROVIDING DIGITAL ECONOMIC GROWTH**

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Abstracts. Currently, the priority task is to move to the digital economy on a global scale and promote the digital economy in the economic and financial sectors, ensuring the use of modern digital technologies. To do this, not only in the central and commercial banking systems but also in small business enterprises, large co-houses, and state organizations, in order to increase the level of provision of digital technologies, it also attracts foreign investments in addition to its domestic ones. As a result, there are certain disadvantages in the economic and financial sectors, despite the fact that the transition to the digital economy system is underway. The following thesis provides conclusions and suggestions for overcoming similar problems.

Keywords: Digital economy, modern technology, economic and financial sector, enterprises,

Content. Today, among all developed countries, the absolute transition to a digitized economic and financial system, improving the economic and social life of the population, finding solutions to many current problems in the economy, and at the same time complete digitization, reducing the human factor, and ending corruption is serving as a foundation for laying and further economic and social development. For this

purpose, information resources center or digital public services have been established in many countries and are being updated with the latest technologies. In developing countries, such areas as e-commerce, distance education, and the creation of online platforms are highly supported in business digitization.

Due to the fact that the issue of digitization and creation of digital infrastructure is on the agenda in the Republic of Uzbekistan, our country is one of the developing countries, and several projects for the introduction and improvement of digitization in all fields, including medicine, education, economic and financial systems and other sectors, and plans strategic tasks. In particular, the Decree No. PF-6079 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 5, 2020 "On the strategy of "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and measures for its effective implementation" was adopted for this purpose.¹

The decree defines a number of priority tasks, including:

- Increase the level of Internet connection of population centers from 78% to 95% by increasing broadband connection portals to 2.5 million, building 20,000 kilometers of optical fiber communication lines and developing mobile communication networks;

- Implementation of more than 400 information systems, electronic services and other software products in various areas of socio-economic development of regions;

- Organization of computer programming training by covering 587,000 people, including 500,000 young people within the framework of the "One Million Programmers" project;

- To improve the digital literacy and skills of governors, state bodies and employees of organizations in the regions, to attach appropriate higher education institutions to train them in information technologies and information security, and to train 12 thousand of their employees in the field of information technologies.

1

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2020-yil 5-noyabrdagi "“Raqamli O'zbekiston — 2030” strategiyasi va uni samarali amalga oshirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida”gi PF-6079 sonli farmoni

Strategic tasks planned on the basis of the following decree are being implemented in our country. In this regard, a lot of attention is being paid to ICT. It is known that the use of information and communication technologies plays an important role in the digitization of the economy. In particular, as a practical result of the above decisions, the use of various smart technologies in the calculation of the use of utility services in the payment system, and at the same time, the establishment of experiments such as "smart house" for the further improvement and management of these services, and in public transport introduction of an automated system and implementation of a cashless payments system, implementation of mechanisms for the implementation of digital insurance based on public-private partnership for the digitization of the insurance system, the use of robotic equipment in real sectors of the economy, and the involvement of robotics and strong IT engineers in large enterprises is observed.

1-table

**On the territory of enterprises and organizations in Uzbekistan, the
number of computers connected to the internet²**

t/r	Regions	2017-year	2018-year	2019-year	2020-year	2021-year
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	12 594	15 431	17 788	21 882	28 666
2	Andijan region	11 972	14 699	17 830	20 173	19 924
3	Bukhara region	14 073	16 041	19 513	23 101	27 573
4	Jizzakh region	12 822	14 200	14 822	9 251	21 025
5	Kashkadarya region	13 179	14 857	18 006	18 631	22 960
6	Navaiy region	11 190	14 490	17 686	18 246	39 367
7	Namangan region	10 499	13 800	17 292	20 408	14 509
8	Samarkand region	23 569	26 955	32 001	33 970	12 753
9	Surkhandarya region	6 907	8 611	9 323	8 840	45 031
10	Sirdarya region	5 488	6 327	7 849	10 245	32 638
11	Tashkent region	18 371	23 393	29 228	36 050	20 297
12	Ferghana region	15 489	18 449	21 508	27 590	207 782
13	Kharazm region	9 410	11 962	14 811	17 600	538 933

² <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/raqamli-iqtisodiyot>

14	Tashkent city	144 896	158 788	175 760	175 926	20 297
	u	310 459	358 003	413 417	441 913	538 933

As we can see from the information listed in the table, on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan, enterprises and organizations in all regions of the republic have demonstrated growth trends in the number of computers connected to the internet. Accordingly, enterprises and organizations located in the territory of Jizzakh region in the year 2020 had 9261 computers connected to the internet, compared to 9261 last year. This figure may be in decline; the organization was established in the year 2021 with 19 924 computers. For this reason, the "Jizzakh" free economic zone in South Korea, in conjunction with the \$11 million annual production capacity of 50 thousand miles of fiber optic cable products, launched the plant.³

In the region of Tashkent and also in the city of Tashkent in the year 2021, the number of computers connected to an internet connection in the enterprise has reached 45 and 206 031 782 during the year 2021. For this reason, two thousand total mobile communication base stations have been installed through the installation of additional 33,7 their population coverage of 95 percent to increase the level of mobile broadband internet in the country. This 2021, in conjunction with not only the capital but also in the territory of the country until the end of the year, Nukus, Urgench, Tashkent, Karshi, Termez, and Tashkent City, too, DOG-park activities were launched because of the branches in this region in various organizations connected to an internet connection, a quick increase in technical reasons.

2-table

³ <https://mitc.uz/uz/news/2340>

Number of personal computers (except servers) in enterprises and organizations located on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁴

t/r	Regions	2017-year	2018-year	2019-year	2020-year	2021-year
1	Republic of Karakalpakstan	41 125	45 483	50 945	53 251	55 510
2	Andijan region	46 409	48 895	54 530	56 344	53 842
3	Bukhara region	41 003	45 294	51 280	55 888	56 058
4	Jizzakh region	25 854	26 976	28 867	18 887	34 016
5	Kashkadarya region	59 141	64 395	67 670	62 434	74 842
6	Navaiy region	35 646	40 031	44 562	46 708	48 364
7	Namangan region	42 643	47 299	52 800	55 071	57 102
8	Samarkand region	69 606	79 084	87 599	86 409	91 490
9	Surkhandarya region	38 829	41 879	40 781	27 291	36 280
10	Sirdarya region	20 254	21 660	23 669	24 435	24 286
11	Tashkent region	60 492	68 944	78 495	81 215	86 668
12	Ferghana region	55 249	62 401	66 245	79 718	84 188
13	Kharazm region	36 675	40 212	45 094	47 518	50 746
14	Tashkent city	280 899	297 347	320 189	319 517	352 751
	Throughout Republic of Uzbekistan	853 825	929 900	1 012 726	1 014 686	1 106 143

While the process of digitizing the digital economy and social society in our country is lagging behind in many areas, we can see that as a result of the above - mentioned decrees and laws, these shortcomings and problems are being put to an end according to the data presented in Table 1 and 2. Analyzing the presence of a personal computer (except servers) in enterprises and organizations of the Department of digital economy of statistics for 2019 and 2021, according to the data presented in Table 2, we can see that the growth rate of our republic in terms of years in the cross-section of Regions is increasing. According to this, the availability of personal computers in enterprises and organizations located in the city of Tashkent amounted to 319,517 units in 2020, a decrease compared to 2019. However, in 2021, it was 352,751 units, a

⁴ <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/raqamli-iqtisodiyot>

significant increase from previous years. This is due to the large amount of investment in ICT provision in the digitization of the economy, which according to the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021 amounted to 11.8 trillion soums (more than 1MILLIARD US dollars).⁵

According to the data presented in the tables above, the availability of personal computers in enterprises and organizations located on the territory of the Republic and the level of internet connection of these technical devices has increased in all the years listed. This is due to the fact that new modern professions (freelancers, programmers, traders, web designers, etc.) are currently developing in the world economy, and the state is paying great attention to this due to the creation of IT parks on the territory of Uzbekistan and the opening of more than 300 new companies as a result of this, digitalization and digital technologies in the economy provide

However, in addition to the implementation and positive results of the various projects listed above, such conditions have not been created in all parts of the Republic's regions. Because of the lack of internet connectivity in rural areas, the need for ICT is low and lags behind in terms of development. To overcome these problems, it is necessary to provide the remote and remote rural areas of our country with fiber-optic internet networks. In addition, the popularization of digital technologies for all areas of the economy, and provide you with a high level of quality in modern information technology, the leading specialists in the field of wide involvement and boosts the skills of the person who conducted regular activities and skills should go. This in turn will help maintain competitive employment and economic problem would be solved in the country to provide help to a significant extent.

⁵ <https://mc.uz/o-zbekistonda-2021-yilda-43-7-mingta-korxonava-tashkilotlar-qurilish-sohasida-faoliyat-yuritgan>

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